

Kinetics of the Alkaline Hydrolysis of *N*-Phenylbenzohydroxamic Acid[#]

KALLOL K. GHOSH* and SHARMISTHA GHOSH

School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur-492 010

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Kinetics of the alkaline hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid have been investigated spectrophotometrically in sodium hydroxide in 10% (v/v) dioxan at several temperatures. The enthalpies and entropies of activation have been evaluated, as also the salt, solvent isotope and solvent (dioxan) effects for the substrate. The effects of substitution have been assessed by means of the Hammett equation. A suitable mechanism has been formulated in accordance with the experimental results.

N-Phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA) is widely acclaimed as a preferred reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of metal ions¹. Some work on the kinetics and mechanistic aspects of the acidic hydrolysis of hydroxamic acids have been carried out by our research group². The present study consists of an investigation of the kinetics of the hydrolysis of PBHA ($C_6H_5C(=O)N(OH)C_6H_5$) in the presence of hydroxide ions. The effects of substitution on the rates of reaction, as well as the kinetics, activation parameters, salt, kinetic solvent isotope and solvent effects, have been considered so as to help postulate the mechanism of alkaline hydrolysis.

Results and Discussion

Rate profile : The hydrolysis was found to be first order in substrate and in hydroxide ion, but as the hydrolysis was carried out in the presence of excess alkali, pseudo-first order rates were ensured. The dependence of k_{ψ} upon NaOH concentrations is shown in Table 1. At all the three temperatures studied (55, 65 and 75°), the pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{ψ}) showed a non-linear dependence on the hydroxide ion concentration. The rate constants decreased initially with OH^- (taken as equal to the stoichiometric concentration of NaOH), reached a

minimum at 3 M NaOH, and then showed an increase with increasing alkali concentration. The pseudo-first order rate constants declined by a factor of about 2.4 over the range $[OH^-] = 0.062$ to 3.0 M. At concentrations of OH^- higher than 3M catalysis seemed to occur. This being the case, the small decline in k_{ψ} (up to 3.0 M NaOH) is due to medium or salt-effect on the uncatalysed reaction. One possible reason for the variation of k_{ψ} with $[NaOH]$ is the effect of solvent. At $[NaOH] > 1$ M incomplete dissociation of NaOH is likely; set against this is the decrease in solvation of OH^- . The net effect is to make OH^- 'more' basic and nucleophilic than indicated by concentration alone. These effects are seen in aqueous solutions and are likely to be accentuated in aqueous dioxan (see solvent effect); our observations may reflect these competing effects with the latter eventually predominating. Alternatively, the variation with $[OH^-]$ may well be due to there being more than one step which is kinetically significant, with perhaps a change from one rate-determining step to another (Scheme 1) within this concentration range. Mashima and Ikeda³ showed a similar rate-decreasing effect for the hydrolysis of formhydrazide in alkaline solution.

Activation parameters : The activation parameters for the alkaline hydrolysis of PBHA were determined

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by measuring the rate of the hydrolysis in different concentrations of NaOH at 55, 65 and 75°. The enthalpy and entropy of activation (Table 2) clearly confirm the nature of a bimolecular reaction. The ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger values vary more or less in a compensating manner. Thus, while ΔH^\ddagger decreased as the alkaline medium concentrated, ΔS^\ddagger became more negative, the overall effect resulting in little variation in ΔS^\ddagger .

TABLE 1—KINETIC DATA FOR HYDROLYSIS OF PBHA AS A FUNCTION OF NaOH IN 10% (v/v) DIOXANE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

NaOH M	$k_w (\times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1})$		
	55°	65°	75°
0.062	6.89	—	—
0.125	6.86	20.0	—
0.25	5.35	15.1	37.2
0.25 ^a	—	27.5	—
0.50	4.71	14.1	35.1
1.0	3.70	10.0	29.9
1.0 ^a	—	16.8	—
1.25	3.58	—	—
1.5	3.24	—	—
2.0	3.17	9.5	24.1
2.0 ^a	—	14.6	—
2.5	3.08	—	—
2.75	2.97	—	—
3.0	2.86	8.12	20.1
3.0 ^a	—	10.9	—
3.5	3.12	9.13	—
4.0	4.58	11.4	26.6
4.0 ^a	—	13.9	—
4.5	8.95	—	—
5.0	12.8	31.4	63.4
5.0 ^a	—	35.8	—
5.5	19.4	—	—

^aIn D₂O.

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR HYDROLYSIS OF PBHA IN 10% (v/v) DIOXAN

NaOH M	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
0.25	89.5 ± 1.3	-55 ± 4.0	105.8 ± 1.0
1.0	96.6 ± 2.9	-37 ± 8.5	107.4 ± 2.2
2.0	93.7 ± 1.9	-46 ± 5.7	107.4 ± 1.4
3.0	90.1 ± 1.4	-59 ± 4.1	107.4 ± 1.0
4.0	80.9 ± 0.5	-83 ± 1.5	105.4 ± 0.4
5.0	73.5 ± 2.6	-97 ± 7.9	102.1 ± 2.0

Salt effect: The effect of salts on the rate constants for the alkaline hydrolysis of PBHA in 10% (v/v) dioxan at 65° is shown in Table 3. The observed

Scheme 1

negative salt-effects are consistent with the existence of a partial positive charge on the carbonyl carbon. This charge would decrease from the reactant to the transition state. Such a decrease in positive charge would correspond to the negative salt-effect. The salt-effects appear to be a function of the extent of delocalisation of charge in the transition state. The more delocalised structures interact more effectively with large cations and are thus stabilised.

TABLE 3—SALT-EFFECT ON HYDROLYSIS OF N-PHENYLBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID AT 65°

Salt M	μ	$k_w (\times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1})$	
		LiCl	NaBr
Nil ^a	1.0	10.0	10.0
0.25	1.25	9.54	9.08
0.50	1.50	9.30	8.59
0.75	1.75	7.50	8.11
1.00	2.00	7.25	7.63
1.25	2.25	7.16	7.52
1.50	2.50	5.99	7.07
1.75	2.75	5.56	6.56
2.00	3.00	4.97	6.24
2.25	3.25	4.46	6.02
2.50	3.50	3.89	5.81
2.75	3.75	3.58	5.53
3.00	4.00	3.10	5.38
3.25	4.25	2.72	5.23

^aNaOH = 1M.

Kinetic solvent isotope effect : The kinetic solvent isotope effects were examined for the alkaline hydrolysis of PBHA in various NaOH concentrations (Table 1). In all cases, rate enhancement in the D₂O solvent system was observed. This effect is a combination of three separate factors : solvation, the relative nucleophilicity of OD⁻ and OH⁻, and the differences between the initial and transition states. The k_{H_2O}/k_{D_2O} values are in the range 0.5–0.8. This may arise from an equilibrium solvent isotope effect on a step prior to the rate-determining step, combined with a secondary solvent isotope effect on the rate-determining step itself. For base catalysed reactions, the kinetic solvent isotope effect does not supply a simple method of distinction among different mechanisms.

Solvent effects : The rate constant for base catalysed hydrolysis of PBHA in diverse aqueous dioxan (0–80%, v/v) medium at 55, 65 and 75° have been determined (Table 4). The rate increase observed when the dioxan content is raised, refers apparently to the uncatalysed reaction (1 M NaOH was used). However, this is not absolutely certain since the change from no catalysis to OH⁻ catalysis could conceivably occur at lower [NaOH] in the dioxan-rich media. This is because OH⁻ may be more active in such media, and also due to the probability of ion aggregation in the dioxan-rich media. The results seem to imply that the rate-determining step has more delocalised charge distribution in its transition state than does the initial PBHA species. The fact that k_{ψ} increases with dioxane content may be explained on the basis of 'desolvation' effect on OH⁻. For systems with comparable initial states, a reaction in which protic solvation is less important would respond more effectively to an increase in dioxan than those in which protic solvation of the transition state is more important. Thus, reactions which involve attack by OH⁻ at a carbonyl group require more protic solvation for the transition state than reactions which proceed by abstraction of a proton by OH⁻ having a delocalised transition state.

Substituent effects : The effects of substitution have been assessed by use of the Hammett equation.

The results of these correlations are shown in Table 5. It has been observed that introduction of electron-attracting groups increases the rate of hydrolysis whereas electron-repelling groups decrease the hydrolysis rate. The ρ values obtained are very small. Both the initial state and the rate-determining transition state are stabilised by groups, but the initial state is slightly less stabilised because the negative charge is further away from the aryl ring than it is in the transition state (Scheme 1).

TABLE 4—RATE CONSTANT FOR HYDROLYSIS OF PBHA WITH 1 M NaOH IN VARIOUS DIOXAN-WATER MIXTURES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Dioxan % (v/v)	$k_{\psi} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$		
	55°	65°	75°
10	0.43	1.09	2.99
20	0.56	1.57	3.86
30	0.76	2.24	5.12
40	1.12	3.12	6.87
50	1.99	4.46	11.8
60	3.02	6.31	15.9
70	4.28	8.78	19.9
80	5.50	15.3	20.8

TABLE 5—ANALYSIS OF RATE DATA OF *para*-SUBSTITUTED PBHA BY HAMMETT EQUATION IN NaOH AT 65°

Nature of substituent	σ	$k_{\psi} (\times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1})$		
		1M	3M	5M
4-OCH ₃	-0.27	11.4	7.72	25.8
4-CH ₃	-0.17	9.39	5.98	29.4
H	0.0	10.0	8.12	31.4
4-F	0.06	13.1	—	—
4-Cl	0.23	12.8	9.07	35.6
4-NO ₂	0.78	16.4	9.52	37.8
ρ		0.263 ± 0.03	0.089 ± 0.02	0.113 ± 0.03
Correlation coefficient		0.983	0.950	0.936
Standard deviation		0.025	0.016	0.022

Correlation of k_{ψ} with acidity function H_- : Anbar *et al.*⁴ derived different equations which relate the observed rate constants of various base-catalysed reactions with the H_- . They summarised the formulations of rate expression of eight types of base-catalysed reactions which may be divided into three groups.

Our results belong to the group containing reactions expected to give linear plot of $\log k_{\psi}$ vs ($H_- + \log a_{H_2O}$) with about unit slope. The plot

Fig 1 Plots of (Δ) $\log k_{\psi}$ vs H_- and (○) $H_- + \log a_{H_2O}$

for our results is shown in Fig. 1, together with the Zucker-Hammett type plot, $\log k_{\psi}$ vs H_- . Both the plots indicate that, in the range of NaOH concentration, two linear parts can be obtained. By analogy with the Bunnett treatment of the acid-catalysed reactions, $(\log k_{\psi} - H_-)$ was plotted against the $\log a_{H_2O}$ shown in Fig. 2. Two linear parts were obtained; in dilute NaOH solutions (0.06–3.0 M) the slope was 1.25, whereas in the range 3.5–5.5 M NaOH, the slope was –0.42. These observations are consistent with two mechanisms.

Mechanism : All the evidence discussed is in favour of the reaction mechanism shown in Scheme 1. We propose two mechanisms, one uncatalysed and the other catalysed by OH^- . The *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamate anion ($PBHA^-$) is present in the initial state, for both mechanisms. The pK_a of $PBHA^5$ is 8.00, indicating that the substrate was completely ionised to $PBHA^-$ over the entire range of $[OH^-]$ used in the study. The mechanism will vary as the OH^- concentration range is changed. The $PBHA^-$ anion is most suitable for a nucleophilic attack, with the negative charge being located at the more remote atom. At low $[OH^-]$, the water molecule or hydroxyl ion attacks the acidic anion and a monoionic tetrahedral intermediate is formed which

Fig 2 Plot of $\log k_{\psi} - H_-$ vs $\log a_{H_2O}$

decomposes to products in a slow step. In strongly basic media, the OH^- ion-catalysed reaction predominates. The concentration of the undissociated substrate would decrease as $[OH^-]$ increases. Therefore, the reaction of the undissociated substrate with OH^- ion is insignificant. In this range, there is a proton abstraction from the hydroxyl group of the intermediate by OH^- , giving the second dianionic intermediate which is followed by its decomposition to the products.

Experimental

The *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid and other *para*-substituted hydroxamic acids were prepared by a standard method⁶. NaOH (A.R.) and dioxan (B.D.H., A.R.) were used as such. The ferric chloride solution used in the colorimetric procedure was prepared by dissolving anhydrous ferric chloride (10 g) (Reidel, L.R.) in distilled water (1 dm³) containing concentrated HCl (100 ml). Kinetic measurements were made by the reported spectrophotometric method⁷ using an EC 5700A spectrophotometer set at 520 nm. Least-squares analysis were carried out on WIPRO 386 computer, under MS-DOS.

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References

1. A. K. MOJUMDER, *Int. Ser. Monogr. Anal. Chem.*, 1972, 50.
2. K. K. GHOSH and S. G. TANDON, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 1004; *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1989, **62**, 1304; K. K. GHOSH, S. K. RAJPUT and K. K. KRISHNANI, *J. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1992, **5**, 39; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **32**, 139; K. K. GHOSH and K. K. KRISHNANI, *J. Chem., Res. (S)*, 1993, 469; *(M)* 1993, 3143.
3. N. MASHIMA and F. IKEDA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1973, **46**, 1371.
4. M. ANBAR, M. BOBTELSKY, D. SAMUEL, B. SILVER and G. YAGIL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 2380.
5. R. MONZYK and A. L. CRUMBLISS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1980, **45**, 4670.
6. U. PRIYADARSHINI and S. G. TANDON, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1967, **12**, 143.
7. K. K. GHOSH and S. G. TANDON, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 1004

